

TECHNICAL EFFICIENCY OF COCOA PRODUCTION IN OYO STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The technical efficiency, determinants of production and the sources of inefficiency in cocoa production in Oyo State are investigated using a stochastic frontier production function which incorporates a model for inefficiency effects. The study employed the use of cross-sectional data from farm survey conducted on a sample of 90 cocoa farmers from seven local government areas in Oyo State. Results showed that, farm size (1%) and fertilizer quantity (1%) are the major factors associated with changes in the output of cocoa production while on the farmer's specific socioeconomic variables, only three, namely: level of education, extension contact and family size were found to be the significant factors accounting for the variation in efficiency among cocoa farmers. The estimated variance parameter (σ^2) for the farmers was 0.5427 (significant at 1%). The estimated gamma (γ) parameter revealed that there are variations in the cocoa output among the cocoa farmers in the area and this variation are due to the differences in their technical efficiencies. The farmers' average technical efficiency is 97%, which suggest an appreciable use of inputs in productivity.

Keywords: Technical Efficiency, Stochastic Frontier, Cocoa farmer.

INTRODUCTION

In Nigeria cocoa is one of the major export crops in terms of foreign exchange earnings. Although its contribution to the total national exports earning during the past two decades dropped considerably due to the enormity of foreign exchange earning of crude petroleum, it still remains the nation most significant agricultural export crop (ICCO, 2001). Cocoa cultivation gained prominence rapidly in Nigeria such that by 1965, Nigeria became the second largest producer in the world. Among others, cocoa production in Nigeria performs the following economic roles. Provision of raw materials for cocoa industries, Provision of revenue for the government, it contributes to aggregate export earnings and provides sources of income to farmers and to many other groups. It also provides market for various agro-chemicals such as herbicides, insecticides, fungicides and fertilizers. It also provides employment for thousands of people both at the farm level and at the industrial processing stage. Cocoa is a concentrated food with high nutritive value. It provides carbohydrate, protein, fat and minerals. Again it is usually used for making beverages, wine, chocolate, cream and livestock feed. In 1962, Nigeria was second largest cocoa producer in the world with about 97% of its total production coming from the southwestern region (Amos, 2007). In recent time, however, the trend seems to have changed with production consistently below 1970 figure, which stood at 30,700 tonnes. The fall in cocoa output may be attributable to two reasons. First, is the Dutch disease, which caused negligence of the agricultural sector by the past administrations due to the discovery of the petroleum resources, which accounts for about 97% of the nation's foreign exchange earnings. Second, is the inherent problem associated with cocoa production such as inadequate investment of public and private sectors in cocoa production, rising costs of production, price instability, differences in management systems and declining productivity due to ageing trees (Abang, 1994).

The magnitude of the problems has affected the position of Nigeria in world production of cocoa bean. By 1994 cocoa production statistics showed that Nigeria was sixth in cocoa production with 135,000 tonnes, while Ghana, Indonesia, Brazil, Malaysia has 245,000 tonnes, 260,000 tonnes, 300,000 tonnes, 220,000 tonnes respectively and Cote'D'ivoire has 840,000 tonnes (Adegeye, 1995).

Due to its importance, the recent Federal Government's concern of diversifying the export base of the nation has placed cocoa in the centre-stage as the most important export tree crop. Evidence has, however, shown that the growth rate of cocoa production has been declining, which has given rise to a fall in the fortunes of the sub-sector among other reasons. Folyan *et al.*, (2006) noted that cocoa production in Nigeria witnessed a downward trend after 1971 season, when its export declined to 216,000 metric tons in 1976, and 150,000 metric tons in

1986, therefore reducing the country's market share to about 6% and to fifth largest producer to date. In fact, the recent cocoa stakeholders forum held in Calabar, Nigeria by the Presidential Initiative on cocoa was to deliberate on the state of the cocoa sub-sector and reach consensus on how investments in the cocoa sub-sector can be strengthened and increased among other issues that bother on the sub sector, in view of the renewed Government's interest to boost cocoa production, domestic utilisation and export.

Quite a number of strategies that attempt to bring about significant increases in cocoa production have been campaigned, one of which is the effective combination of measures aimed at increasing the level of farm resources, and making efficient use of the resources committed to the cocoa production and combining the enterprises in an optimal manner.

The crucial role of efficiency in increasing agricultural output has been widely recognized by researchers and policy makers alike. Increasing the level of efficiency in cocoa production farmers who operate optimally along their production function while being much less successful in shifting from a production function to a higher one could help in the resolution of the obvious decline in the agricultural exports with respect to the important export crops like cocoa, kolanut, rubber and cashew and improving the welfare of farmers. It is no surprise therefore, that considerable effort has been devoted to the analysis of farm level efficiency in developing countries, Nigeria inclusive. An underlying premise behind much of this work is that if farmers were not making efficient use of existing technology, then efforts designed to improve efficiency would be more cost effective than introducing new technologies as a means of increasing agricultural output. (Belbase and Grabowski, 1985). This study examined the economic factors that determine production efficiency and the sources of inefficiency of cocoa farmers in Oyo State.

HYPOTHESES

Ho 1: Socio economic characteristics of cocoa farmers have no effect on their level of technical efficiency in the state.

Ho 2: Cocoa farmers in Oyo State are technically efficient in production.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Ajibefun and Daramola (1999) defined efficiency in agriculture in association with the possibility of farm's production to attain optimum level of output from a given bundle of input at least cost. Farrell (1957) has derived the three components of efficiency recognizable in the economic literature. They include: (i) Technical efficiency, (ii) Allocative efficiency, and (iii) Economic efficiency.

Yao and Liu (1998) defined technical efficiency as the ability to produce maximum output from a given set of inputs, given the available technology. Technical efficiency according to (Nwaru, 2003) refers to the ability of a given set of entrepreneurs to employ the best practice in any industry so that not more than the necessary amount of a given set of resources is used in producing the best level of output.

M.J Farrell originated the current interest in efficiency measurements. Farrell (1957) proposed an approach that distinguishes between technical and allocative efficiency. Technical efficiency refers to the ability of producing a given level of output with a minimum quantity of inputs under a given technology. Allocative efficiency refers to the choice of the optimal input proportions given relative prices. Economic or total efficiency is the product of technical and allocative efficiency. Farrell's model, which is known as a deterministic nonparametric frontier (Forsund, *et al*, 1980), attributes any deviation from the frontier to inefficiency and imposes no functional form on the data. Several extensions of Farrell deterministic model have been made by economists such as Aigner and Chu, (1968), and Greene, (1980) among others.

Thus, Battese (1992) showed a more general presentation of Farrell's concept of the production function (or frontier) as depicted in figure 1 below involving the original input and output values. The horizontal axis represents the (vector of) inputs, X, associated with producing the output, Y. The observed input-output values are below the production frontier, given that farms do not attain the maximum output possible for the inputs involved, given the technology available, A measure of the technical efficiency of the farm which produces output, Y, with inputs, X, denoted by point A, is given by Y/Y^* , where Y^* is the "frontier output" associated with the level of inputs, X (see point B). This is a measure of technical efficiency, which is dependent on the levels of the inputs involved.

Figure 1: Technical efficiency of firms in input-output space.
Source: Battese, 1992.

Empirical estimation of efficiency is normally done with the methodology of stochastic frontier production function. The stochastic frontier production model has the advantage of allowing simultaneous estimation of individual technical and allocative efficiencies of the respondent farmers as well as determinants of technical efficiency (Battese and Coelli, 1995).

The ideas of production function can be illustrated with a farm using n inputs: X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n , to produce output Y , efficient transformation of inputs into output is characterized by the production function $f(X)$, which shows the maximum output obtainable from various inputs used in production. The stochastic frontier production function independently proposed by Aigner *et al.*, (1977) and Meeusen and Van Den Broeck, (1977) assumes that maximum output may not be obtained from a given input or a set of inputs because of the inefficiency effects.

It can be written as:

$$Y_i = f(Xa_i; \beta) + \varepsilon_i \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Where, Y_i is the quantity of agricultural output,
 Xa is a vector of input quantities and,
 β is a vector of parameters
 ε_i is an error term defined as:

$$\varepsilon_i = V_i - U_i \quad i = 1, 2, \dots n \text{ farms} \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

V_i is a symmetric component that accounts for pure random factors on production, which are outside the farmers' control such as weather, disease, topography, distribution of supplies, combined effects of unobserved inputs on production etc. and U_i is a one-sided component, which captures the effects of inefficiency and hence measures the shortfall in output Y_i from its maximum value given by the stochastic frontier $f(Xa; \beta) + V_i$. The model is expressed as:

$$Y_i = \exp (X_i \beta + V_i - U_i) \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

The technical efficiency of production of the i -th farmer in the appropriate data set, given the levels of his inputs, is defined by:

$$TE_i = \exp(-U_i) \dots\dots\dots(4)$$

From equations (3) and (4), the two components V_i and U_i are assumed to be

independent of each other, where V_i is the two-sided, normally distributed random error ($V_i \sim N(0, \sigma_v^2)$), and U_i is the one-sided efficiency component with a half normal distribution ($U_i \sim / N(0, \sigma_u^2)$). Y_i and X_i are as defined earlier. The β 's are unknown parameters to be estimated together with the variance parameters.

The variances of the parameters, symmetric V_i and one-sided U_i , are σ_v^2 and σ_u^2 respectively and the overall model variance given as σ^2 are related thus:

$$\sigma^2 = \sigma_v^2 + \sigma_u^2 \dots\dots\dots(5)$$

The measures of total variation of output from the frontier, which can be attributed to technical efficiency, are lambda (λ) and gamma (γ) (Battese and Corra, 1977) while the variability measures derived by Jondrow *et al.*, (1982) are presented by equations (4) and (5):

$$\lambda = \frac{\sigma_u}{\sigma_v} \dots\dots\dots (6)$$

$$\gamma = \frac{\sigma_u^2}{\sigma_v^2} \dots\dots\dots (7)$$

On the assumption that V_i and U_i are independent and normally distributed, the parameters $\beta, \sigma^2, \sigma_u^2, \sigma_v^2, \lambda$ and γ can be estimated by method of Maximum Likelihood Estimates (MLE), using the computer program FRONTIER Version 4.1 (Coelli, 1996). This computer program also computed estimates of technical and allocative efficiencies.

The farm specific technical efficiency (TE) of the i -th farmer can be estimated using the expectation of U_i conditional on the random variable (ϵ_i) as shown by Battese and Coelli (1995). The TE of an individual farmer is defined in terms of the ratio of the observed output to the corresponding frontier output given the available technology, that is:

$$TE_i = \frac{Y_i}{Y_i^*} = \frac{\exp(X_i\beta + V_i - U_i)}{\exp(X_i\beta + V_i)} = \exp(-U_i) \dots\dots\dots (8)$$

(Tadesse and Krishnamoorthy, 1997)

So that:

$$0 \leq TE \leq 1$$

METHODOLOGY

(i) The data

This study was carried out in the following Local Government Areas of Oyo State: Ona-Ara, Akinyele, Oluyole, Ido, Lagelu, Egbeda and Afijio Local Government Areas of Oyo state respectively. These are the major cocoa producing areas in the state (CDU Bulletin, 2007). They are considered on the basis of economic comparative advantage and soil suitability especially they are the major cocoa producing area where cocoa farmers can be found. The state lies in the equatorial rainforest belt and the rainfall around this area varies from 155mm to 1800mm per annum. There is distinct wet season from April to late October and dry season from November to March, the areas have a mean annual temperature of 26.2 degree Celsius, the humidity is high between July and December and low between December and February.

The luxuriant forests are arranged in two or three layers consisting of undergrowth, medium higher trees and tall tree. The variety of plant species found here is one of the richest in the world (CDU Bulletin, 2007).

Multistage sampling procedure was adopted. Firstly, purposive sampling technique was employed in the selection of seven Local Government Areas (LGAs) in Oyo State i.e Ona-Ara, Akinyele, Oluyole, Ido, Lagelu, Egbeda and Afijio Local Government Areas of Oyo state respectively. They are considered on the basis of economic comparative advantage and soil suitability especially they are the major cocoa producing area where cocoa farmers can be found (CDU Bulletin, 2007). Secondly, thirty percent (30%) number of villages was considered from the list of registered villages in the seven selected L.G.As. Therefore, use of random number table was employed in the selection of three (3) villages from Ona Ara LGA, three (3) villages from Oluyole LGA, three (3) villages from Ido LGA, four (4) villages from Akinyele LGA, three (3) villages from Lagelu LGA, two (2) villages from Egbeda LGA and two (2) villages from Afijio LGA respectively, making a total of twenty (20) villages. Thirty percent (30%) of the registered cocoa farmers from these villages were considered, to give 90 cocoa farmers as respondents. Data were collected from the farm households with a structured and validated questionnaire. Data were collected on the socio-economic characteristics of the farmer, cropping patterns, production activities in terms of inputs, outputs and their prices using the cost-route approach.

(ii) *The model*

In the analysis of the data for cocoa producing farmers, stochastic production frontier was employed- using the variant of the stochastic production analysis adopted by Coelli and Battese, (1996) and Dawson *et al*, (1991). It is assumed that the farm frontier production function can be written as:

$$Q = f(X_i; \beta) \dots\dots\dots (9)$$

Where, Q is the quantity of cocoa output,
 X_i is a vector of input quantities,
 β is a vector parameter.

The model of the stochastic frontier production for the estimation of the TE was specified as:

$$\ln Y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln X_1 + \beta_2 \ln X_2 + \beta_3 \ln X_3 + \beta_4 \ln X_4 + \beta_5 \ln X_5 + V_i - U_i \dots\dots\dots (10)$$

Where subscript i refers to the observation of the ith farmer, and

- Y = Cocoa output (kg)
- X_1 = Farm size under cocoa cultivation (ha)
- X_2 = Herbicide quantity (litre)
- X_3 = Fungicides quantity (litre)
- X_4 = labour (man-days)
- X_5 = Fertilizer Quantity (kg)
- β_i 's = the parameters estimated
- ln's = natural logarithms
- V_i = the two-sided, normally distributed random error
- U_i = the one-sided inefficiency component with a half-normal distribution.

In this study, the technical inefficiency was measured by the mode of the truncated normal distribution (i.e. U_i) as a function of socio-economic factors (Yao and Liu, 1998). Thus, the technical efficiency was simultaneously estimated. The determinants of the technical efficiency were defined by:

$$U_i = \delta_0 + \delta_1 Z_1 + \delta_2 Z_2 + \delta_3 Z_3 + \delta_4 Z_4 + \delta_5 Z_5 \dots\dots\dots (11)$$

Where: U_i = technical inefficiency of the ith farmer

- Z_1 = Age of farmer (yrs)
- Z_2 = Family Size (number)
- Z_3 = Year of farming experience (yrs)
- Z_4 = Educational level (school attended)
- Z_5 = Extension Contact (Yes = 1, No =0)

The parameters of the stochastic frontier function are estimated by the method of maximum likelihood using the computer program FRONTIER version 4.1 (Coelli, 1994).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

(a) Socio-economic characteristics of respondents.

The mean age of the sampled cocoa farmers was 49 years, headed by majorly male, married and had attained at least primary school level education. The average farm household surveyed had 6 family members with farm size per household averaged 1.61 hectares of cultivated land in different locations. The mean quantity of fertilizer used by the cocoa is 27.24kg/ha with the mean quantity of herbicides of 1.22 liters/ha while that of average fungicides is 1.97 litres/ha.

Farm operations relied primarily on hired labour and traditional farming practices. Mean years of farming experience was 28, majority of them used their personal saving for cocoa production while majority of the cocoa farmers in the study area belong to cocoa association which could be as a matter of choices and interest of individuals towards the association while some farmers sees cocoa association as a means of siphon their little profit.

(b) Stochastic Frontier Estimation

The frontier function was estimated using maximum likelihood estimation approach (MLE) through the FRONTIER 4.1 programme developed and licensed by Coelli (1994). The results of MLE are given in Table 1

Table 1: Maximum Likelihood Estimates of the Determinants of Technical Efficiency in Cocoa Production in Oyo State.

Variable	Parameter	Coefficient	T-ratio
Production Factors			
Constant	β_0	0.2407	38.106
Farm Size	β_1	0.8953	15.392***
Herbicide Quantity	β_2	0.3442	1.1956
Fungicide Quantity	β_3	0.2347	0.8459
Labour	β_4	0.4336	1.1050
Fertilizer Quantity	β_5	0.3872	3.0558***
Inefficiency Factors			
Constant	Z_0	-0.1532	-0.2558
Age of Farmer	Z_1	0.1263	1.0472
Family Size	Z_2	0.2455	5.3772***
Year of Farming Experience	Z_3	-0.8290	-0.5116
Educational Level	Z_4	0.4017	4.4553***
Extension Contact	Z_5	0.6180	2.3172**
Variance Parameters			
Sigma Squared	σ^2	0.5427	5.2353***
Gamma	γ	0.6388	3.3948***
Log Likelihood Function		10.73	

Notes: *** =1% level; ** = 5%; * = 10%.

Source: Computer printout of Frontier 4.1

Table 1 shows the maximum likelihood parameter estimates of the Cobb-Douglas stochastic frontier production function for cocoa farmers in the study area. Results in the table showed that the estimate of σ^2 (0.5427), that is sigma-squared is relatively large, statistically significant and different from zero at 0.01 level. This indicates a good fit of the model and the correctness of the specified distributional assumptions of the composite error term. This result is consistent with the findings of Xu and Jeffrey (1995) and Ajibefun and Aderinola (2003) in their various investigations.

The estimated gamma (γ) parameter defined as $\gamma = \delta u^2 / (\delta u^2 + \delta v^2)$ is high estimated to be 63.8 percent, which can be interpreted to mean that the differences between actual (observed) and frontier output are dominated by technical inefficiency. The results suggest that about 63.8% of the variation in cocoa output among cocoa farmers in the study area is due to the differences in their technical efficiencies. This result is consistent with the findings of Dawson *et al.*, (1991), Yao and Liu, (1998); Ajibefun *et al.*, (2002); Ajibefun and Aderinola (2004).

(c) Production Elasticities

Table 1 shows that the coefficients of farm size and fertilizer quantity used carried the expected positive signs and were significant at the one percent level. Their output elasticities indicated that an increase of 1 percent in farm size (hectare) and fertilizer quantity used, will lead to 0.8953 and 0.3872 per cent increase in output of arable crops respectively. Farm size had the highest coefficient, with a value 0.8953 in the preferred model and by implication the farm size used existed as the most important input that impact on cocoa output of cocoa farmers in the state. Though for every unit increase in land used there is less than proportionate increase in cocoa output. The sum of the elasticities indicated that the farmers were operating in the increasing returns to scale stage of production in the short run. In this regards, optimum efficiency of production has not been achieved and the technologies for cocoa production were underutilized below the maximum technical efficiency. Farm size and fertilizer quantity used were found to be important factors in explaining output.

(d) Sources of Inefficiency

The estimated parameters of the inefficiency model in the stochastic frontier models of cocoa farmers in Oyo State are presented in Table 1. The analysis of the inefficiency model shown in Table 1 showed that the signs and significance of the estimated coefficients in the inefficiency model have important policy implications on the technical efficiency (TE) of cocoa farmers in Oyo State. The coefficients of family size, educational level and extension contact were positive while the years of farming experience were negative. The coefficient of level of education, family size and extension contact variable is estimated to be positive as expected and statistically significant at the 1 percent and 5 percent level respectively. The findings above revealed that the family size, educational level and extension contact tend to increase the level of technical inefficiency of cocoa farmers while the years of farming experience tend to reduce the level of technical inefficiency of the farmers. The above findings were not conformed to *a priori* expectation and were incongruent to the findings of Ajibefun and Daramola, 1999 and Seyoum *et al.*, 1998. The reasons for family size, educational level and extension contact contributing to the inefficiency level of the farmers may include inefficient and inadequate family labour input, lack of proper supervision of their farms due to other profitable off-farm activities as well as trivialization of proven cocoa production information on personal grounds. Farmers with formal education tend to be more technically efficient in cocoa production, due presumably to their enhanced technical competence, which enables them to produce close to the frontier output. Also, farmers with education respond readily to the use of improved technology and tend to cope more with complexities associated with improved technology. Farmers who had more extension visits, teachings and training, tend to be more technically efficient in cocoa production. Extension teachings and training affords the farmer the opportunity to learn improved technologies and how to acquire needed inputs and services as rightly observed by Ayanwale (1995).

Table 2 shows the predicted technical efficiency estimates obtained using the estimated stochastic frontier models for the cocoa farmers in the study area. The predicted cocoa farmers' specific technical efficiency (TE) for the farmers' indices ranged from a minimum of 85% to a maximum of 100%, with a mean of 97%.

Table 2: Efficiency Range of Frequency Distribution of Technical Efficiencies of Cocoa farmers in Oyo State.

Efficiency Score (%)	Technical Efficiency Cocoa Farmers	
	Frequency	Percentage
0.85 – 0.90	13	14.44
0.91 – 0.94	11	12.23
0.95 – 1.0	66	
Total	90	73.33
		100.0
Mean %	97%	
Minimum %	85%	
Maximum %	100%	

Source: Result from data analysis, 2010.

Table 2 show the predicted cost savings according to efficiency indicator by the cocoa farmers in the study area. Thus, in the short run, an average cocoa farmer have the scope of increasing their cocoa production by about 3% by adopting the technology and techniques used by the best practiced (most efficient) cocoa farmers. Such cocoa farmers could also realize 3% cost savings (i.e.1 – [97/100]) in order to achieve the TE level of his most efficient counterpart (Bravo-Ureta and Evenson, 1994). The above findings unfolds the capacity of an average cocoa farmers to increase their technical efficiency level to a tune of 3% and in turn attain a cost-saving status of about 3% that the most technically efficient cocoa farmers had enjoyed in their cocoa production enterprise using the available production techniques and technology in the study area.

(e) Test of Hypotheses

The hypothesis is defined thus: $H_{01}: \delta_1 = \delta_2 = \delta_3 = \delta_4 = \delta_5 = 0$, where δ_i is the individual explanatory coefficient (i.e. socio-economic variables of the farmers have no effect on the level of technical efficiency of cocoa farmers). The test used was the generalized likelihood ratio test and was conducted at $\alpha = 0.05$ given a degree of freedom 88 for the farmers. Table 3 showed the results of generalized likelihood ratio test for the coefficients of the inefficiency model of the stochastic frontier production function for the cocoa farmers. It has been seen that only the family size and educational level was significant and as such the null hypothesis was rejected for only the family size and educational level among the other inefficiency variables of the cocoa farmers. Therefore, it can be concluded that not only the production function variables determine TE of cocoa farmers; there exist a significant inefficiency effect from two of their inefficiency variables.

The generalized likelihood ratio test statistic is defined by:

$$X_c^2 = -2 \ln(L(H_o) - L(H_a))$$

Where $L(H_o)$ is the value of the log-likelihood function under the null hypothesis (i.e., the restricted model likelihood function) and $L(H_a)$ is the value of the log-likelihood function under the alternative hypothesis (i.e., the unrestricted model likelihood function). If the null hypothesis is true, the log-likelihood ratio test has a mixed Chi-square distribution with degree of freedom equals the number of parameters excluded in the traditional average response function. This method was used to test for the first hypothesis. The decision rule is that the null hypothesis is accepted if the computed Chi-square is less than the tabulated Chi-square at 5% level of significance and a given degree of freedom.

Table 3: Generalized likelihood Ratio Test for the Significance of Coefficients of the Socio-Economic Variables of the Inefficiency Models of Cocoa Farmers.

H ₀₁ : Socio-Economic variables of the farmers have no effect on their level on the Technical Efficiency (H ₀ : $\delta_1 = \delta_2 = \delta_3 = \delta_4 = \delta_5 = 0$)							
Variables	Parameter	Coefficient	T-Ratio	T-Critical	X ² Computed	X ² 0.05,5	Decision
Age of Farmer	δ_1	0.1263	1.0472	1.655	10.11	11.07	Accept H ₀
Family size	δ_2	0.2455	5.3772	1.655	14.04	11.07	Reject H ₀
Years of Farming Experience	δ_3	-0.8290	-0.5116	1.655	9.48	11.07	Accept H ₀
Educational Level	δ_4	0.4017	4.4553	1.655	21.02	11.07	Reject H ₀
Extension contact	δ_5	0.6180	0.3172	1.655	11.07	11.07	Accept H ₀

Source: MLE Diagnostic Statistics Critical X² were obtained.

The results of the generalized likelihood ratio test indicate that hypothesis 1 which specifies that the explanatory variables in the model for the inefficiency factors have zero coefficients is hereby rejected. This implies that the explanatory variables in the model contributed significantly in the explanation of efficiency in cocoa production in Oyo State.

CONCLUSION AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

The study has shown that cocoa farmers in the study area were technically efficient and technical efficiency in cocoa production could be also improved. Farm resources were optimally allocated but also suggesting a scope for improvement. Farm size was positive and significantly influenced farmers' efficiency. The need for emphasizing the expansion of area under cocoa cultivation becomes compulsory as there are advantages of having large sized farms. Cocoa production in the study area should be managed by young and better-educated farmers who will be able to adopt the new and improved technologies which are both labour and cost - saving in nature bearing in mind the goals of maximizing the use of endowed resources of land, labour, capital and others in the study area. There should be improvement in the farmers' access to extension services and technical advisory services with special emphasis placed on the training of farmers for easy adoption of improved technology such that whatever technology is in place, there will be efficiency of its usage. There should be provision of institutional credit to farmers on timely basis and with easy access to such credit facilities. This measure would allow cocoa farmers to purchase inputs like fertilizer, fungicides, herbicides and modern farm implements and as such expand their initial land area allotted to crop production.

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